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If my observations in this article are adequate to what is happening, we are facing a world in transformation, in transition. A complex world made up of many factors whose overlapping and crossing creates novelty. The purpose of these pages was twofold: to invite to ask oneself whether one's research is determined by mental schemes that respond to conditions of the past (thus making it ineffective for the present and for the future); to invite to raise questions about the transformations necessary for future researches on the history of Christianity in the context of a transition to a new era.

Keywords: A new era, Mental schemes of the past, New mental schemes, History of Christianity, Globalization.

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In the argument from silence ("I have no evidence of *p*; if *p* were true, I would have evidence of *p*; therefore *p* is false"), the critical issue is whether the conditional is secure. In historical studies, silence must be understood as silence in relation to a particular evidentiary set. An inference *e silentio* becomes unsafe when the evidentiary set is known to be defective; and when the kind of data of which *p* is an instance is not the kind of evidence that has survived. In neither case is an inference *e silentio* safe.

Keywords: Philology, Conjectural Emendations, Christ Groups, Eucharistic Meals.

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The apparently disorganized visionary content of the book of Revelation suggests a disoriented and perhaps even psychotropic visionary. Nonetheless, the ecstatic Seer's literary record of

that apocalyptic journey is a multi-valent masterpiece that uses three literary devices simultaneously to recount a linear narrative and a reiterative structure. This two-part article focuses, in part 1, upon how John's use of the "space/time referent" and the linguistic equivalents of the two clauses "and I saw" and "after these things I saw" also elucidate coherent structures for Jewish prophetic visionary texts, and, in part 2, upon how they provide structure for Jewish apocalypses. Distinctive to John's Apocalypse, however, is the fact that it leverages those three literary devices to create a reiterative structure that serves implicitly to reinforce his explicit statements to his seven *ekklesia* communities that the return of Jesus the Jewish *Christos* was imminent.

Keywords: Revelation, Apocalypse, Prophecy, Vision, Space-time.

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I fully agree with Rebillard that, unlike many earlier studies, we should not try to reduce the early martyrdom accounts to just a reflection of their court cases. While the more authentic ones sometimes come close to being eye-witness reports, they always contain theological reflections and often literary embellishments as well. However, it is also important to stress that this examination should be as unprejudiced as possible. To exclude beforehand internal evidence robs the historian of an important source of information. To avoid analysing earlier discussions makes one invent the wheel again. In the end, there is no satisfactory solution to the problem of historical authenticity that covers all cases, and we must rest content with the fact that no reconstruction of the original form of the accounts can claim absolute certainty. Like any other historical source, these texts, too, must be examined on their own terms.

Keywords: *Passion of Perpetua*, Martyrdom, Historical authenticity, Eye-witness reports, Absolute certainty.

Revisiting Gospel of Thomas, logion 61

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This introductory article contextualizes the essays by Daniele Tripaldi and René Falkenberg on *Gos. Thom. 61* within the current debate on the "Old Philology" and the "New Philology," as well as on the Nag Hammadi Codices. It also provides some brief methodological considerations on the study of the *Gospel of Thomas* and other early Christian texts.

Keywords: *Gospel of Thomas*, Old Philology, New Philology, Nag Hammadi Codices, Late Antique Egypt.

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Keywords: *Constitutio textus*, Philological *Divination*, Semantic Diffractions, Lexicon of Isolation and Solitude, Greek *Gospel of Thom.*

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Keywords: New Philology, Coptic Literature, *Gospel of Thomas*, Salome, Eucharist.

Ancient Christianity

Milan Vukomanović and Bojana Radovanović, <i>A Quest for Epiphanius' Collyridians – The Pilgrimesses of the Mother of God</i>	141
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This article proposes a new hypothesis regarding the background and religious activity of the fourth-century Christian community of Collyridians, to which Epiphanius of Salamis dedicated an entire chapter of his *Panarion*. Epiphanius provides only a few details about the origin of this sect, but even this limited amount of data betrays authenticity. The heterodoxy of the Collyridians has rarely been examined in the scope of the wider religious, cultural and social-historical frameworks pertaining to Roman and Early Christian history. This context includes not only the issues of Mariology, but also women's religious service, non-Christian religious landscapes, and travel and pilgrimage in Late Antiquity. Epiphanius' account has been observed through the combined contextual, social-historical and philological lenses. In order to elucidate the origin and character of the Collyridian ritual practice, this essay has paid more attention to both the original geographical setting and the later movement of this sect, pointing to their ultimate religious destination. Our main thesis is that the Collyridians fled from Thrace and Scythia to Roman Arabia under the Gothic persecution of Christians. In the aftermath of this event, they performed their pilgrimage at the most ancient *locus sanctus* pertaining to the Virgin Mary in Judea, known as Kathisma, and situated halfway from Jerusalem to Bethlehem.

Keywords: Collyridians, Epiphanius' of Salamis *Panarion*, Heterodoxy, Kathisma, Pilgrimage.

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Keywords: Paul-Henri Thiry d'Holbach, *Histoire critique de Jésus Christ*, Book Censorship, Holy Office, Censorship Notes, Jesus in Modern Thought.

Apocalypse Now?

Apocalyptic Imageries in Contemporary American Political Discourse

Jeanne Petrolle, *Apocalypse Never: Tony Kushner's Angels in America Counters the End of the World*..... 189

Tony Kushner's Pulitzer-prize winning play *Angels in America: A Gay Fantasia on National Themes* (1991–92) uses apocalyptic motifs—end times, revelation, angels, prophecy, new heaven—to analyze American politics. The two-part play laments political corruption and social cruelty while imagining the emergence of an all-inclusive, multiracial, multiethnic polis in which unlikely partners achieve unity across difference in a utopian community of care. Kushner's uses of apocalyptic demonstrate that the genre offers religious and secular authors alike a powerful symbolic vocabulary for political discourse. In the United States, apocalyptic tropes are often made to serve conservative or reactionary political agendas, but Kushner's play illuminates the progressive potential of the ancient text's visual language; *Angels in America* exemplifies a variation of the genre theologian Catherine Keller calls *counter-apocalypse*.

Keywords: Tony Kushner, *Angels in America*; Gay Culture; LGBTQ Literature; Apocalypse; American Politics and the Bible.

Erik Grayvold, *Marks and Tweets: Apocalyptic Imagery in the US Anti-Vaxxer Movement* 213

The article explains the reception of Revelation 13:1–14:1 by the anti-vaccination movement in the United States and how it impacts political discourse in the United States. Given the pericope's already politically charged context, the movement's current use of the text increases the text's political nature and transforms political adversaries into monsters or beasts, thus making an already polarizing issue more extreme. Initially, the anti-vaccination movement invoked the Mark of the Beast by alleging that the coronavirus vaccines carried a microchip. Later, individuals such as Representative Marjorie Taylor Greene used social media to shift the message to refer instead to vaccine passports as the Mark of the Beast to attack President Joseph Biden.

Keywords: the Mark of the Beast, Vaccines, Christian nationalism, Social media, Marjorie Taylor Green, Kanye West.

Lorenzo Cozzi, *Apocalypse and Prophecy in Nicholas of Lyra's Commentary. Beyond the State of the Art* 241

In this article, I intend to retrace the fundamental coordinates of the *Commentary on the Apocalypse* by Nicholas of Lyra (1270–1349) and its critical reception in contemporary scholarship. Noting that in the current bibliographic baggage the observations have focused exclusively on the analysis of the sources and on the spread of Nicholas' work, I therefore undertake to open a further level of analysis. The pivot of this new perspective is epitomised in the concept of prophecy, which, emerging in the conclusion of the *Commentary*, allows us to reconnect with renewed depth the work of the Lyranus to its context of provenance.

Keywords: Apocalyptic Thought, Theory of Prophecy, History of the Franciscan Order, Exegesis, John's Apocalypse, Nicholas of Lyra.

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Milan Vukomanović and Bojana Radovanović

A Quest for Epiphanius' Collyridians – The Pilgrimesses of the Mother of God

On a given day of the year, some women would gather on Arabian soil, bake bread-cakes as an offering to the Virgin Mary, and place them on an improvised altar covered with a linen cloth. This form of worship took root in Thrace and northern Scythia, whence it spread to Roman Arabia. This all happened sometime before the late fourth century, when Epiphanius, bishop of Salamis (ca. 315–403), wrote his account on the sect he named the Collyridians, for which he reserved the seventy-ninth chapter of his *Panarion* (374–377).¹

Thus far, a significant academic output on the Collyridians has been produced.² However, their “heresy” has rarely been examined in the scope of the wider religious, cultural and social-historical frameworks pertaining to Roman and Early Christian history. Some of the prevailing research areas within which the Collyridians found their well-deserved place include the issues of Mariology, women’s religious service (ritual studies), orthodoxy and heresy, pre-Christian and non-Christian religious landscapes. Thus, the phenomenon of the Collyridians came to be observed through specific lenses: some saw in this sect elements pinpointing to the highly debated issues of the female priesthood, while others identified heterodox women resembling the Montanists; some of the studies referred to pagan influences in the formation of the Collyridian cult, while others tackled the dogmas related

¹ Williams 2013, 637–645. The name *Collyridians* derives from the Greek word denoting a small cake or a loaf of bread of a cylindrical shape (*kollyris*, κολλύρις) which the women from this sect offered to the Virgin Mary as part of their peculiar ritual.

² Dölger 1929; Kateusz 2013; Kraemer 1992, 157–173; Benko 2004, 170–195; Kearns 2008, 283–284; Avner 2011; Shoemaker 2006a; 2006b; 2008a; 2008b; 2011; 2016, 130–228; Carroll 1986, 42–47; Mimouni 2011, 295–318.

to the developmental thread of early Mariology.³ Consequently, several points of examination remain to be addressed and re-evaluated, in an attempt to fill in the remaining lacunae. Firstly, it would be important to take into consideration the “forgotten” secondary literature produced prior to the Enlightenment period. Secondly, Epiphanius’ account on the Collyridians could be observed through combined contextual, social-historical and philological lenses. Thirdly, in order to elucidate some insufficiently transparent formative elements of the origin and character of the Collyridian practice, it is necessary to pay some more attention to the original geographical setting and later movement of this sect, pointing to “Arabia”⁴ as their ultimate destination. Suffice it to say at this point that even Epiphanius was not quite certain about the specific traits and character of the Collyridian ritual (Pan. II, 79, 3; Pan. II, 79, 9, 4).

As for Epiphanius’ informants, Frank Williams suggests that “sources of this Sect are oral,” which is clearly indicated by the *Panarion* (II, 79, 1, 2): “... and word of it has reached me.” Namely, Epiphanius is the only available historical source for the Collyridians (apart from the brief mention by Leontius of Byzantium that we will also tackle below). Furthermore, his letter to Arabia constitutes a primary written source regarding the period and events related to Collyridian Mariolatry. The Arabian heresy that refutes Mary’s virginity is described in the *Panarion* (II, 78.1, 1) and Epiphanius states that this information is “referred to [his] humble self by some of those pious ones” (ἀνηνέχθη δὲ τῆ ἡμῶν ταπεινότητι περὶ τούτων ὑπὸ τινῶν εὐλαβῶν). In all likelihood, this would indicate that the information reached Epiphanius through some other, presumably local Christian source. This source was also opposed to the described heterodox views, and, accordingly, was able to convey these observations to Epiphanius, probably their bishop. However, in the case of other sects, Epiphanius normally referred to the Church Fathers and heresiologists (such as Origen, Jerome, Eusebius, Justin Martyr, Irenaeus of Lyon, Hippolytus), or else to his own personal knowledge.⁵ Unfortunately, in the case of the Collyridian sect, one lacks any information stemming from these or other ancient authors. Finally, Epiphanius often dictated his texts, drawing, at the same time, from other early

³ Cf. Dölger 1929, 116–118; Benko 2004, 193–195; Kraemer 1992, 166–167; Shoemaker 2008a; 2008b; Kateusz 2013.

⁴ It is clear from the *Panarion* that Epiphanius’ references to “Arabia” imply the geography of the Roman *Provincia Arabia* (Arabia Petraea), an area “on the borders of Palestine” (Pan. II, 66, 1, 7). When he refers to “the land called Arabia Felix,” the region in the interior of the Arabian Peninsula, he explicitly states that (Pan. I, 4, 1, 6).

⁵ Williams 2009, 123–130. For example, his account of the Nazoreans (Pan. II, 29), according to Williams, “seems to be based on Epiphanius’ personal knowledge, though he has conjectured its history from passages in scripture and Eusebius.”

Christian documents, such as, for example, the *Protevangelium of James* in his two chapters on Marian heresy.⁶

In the year when Epiphanius was elevated to the episcopal rank (367), and even before writing his *Panarion* (prior to 375–378), another ecclesiastical authority was particularly prominent in the same region. Athanasius (ca. 296/298–373), influential church father and bishop,⁷ was still very active in nearby Alexandria. A heated debate on the status of the Virgin Mary was taking place several decades before the Council of Ephesus (431), when it reached its peak. In the meantime, various alternative doctrines were on the church agenda, with some heterodox groups probably going so far as to treat Mary as a divine being or perhaps even virgin goddess. It is exactly in this kind of polemical milieu of the late fourth century that Epiphanius was able to notice the peculiar Collyridian rite.

The latest reliable mention of the Collyridians (as Philomarianites) in a primary source is dated in the sixth century and comes from Leontius of Byzantium (485–543), a monk and a theologian.⁸ Leontius mentions some “simple people [...] who honor the Virgin more than is appropriate” (Τινὲς... τῶν ἀπλουστέρων... πλέον ἢ προσήκε τὴν Παρθένον ἀποσεμνύοντες).⁹ Later on, in the same document, he asks: “Does the bread which is offered as a symbol of the body of Christ obtain any greater blessing than the bread sold in the market, or the loaves that the Philomarianites offer in Mary’s name?”¹⁰ This account was composed a full century after the Council of Ephesus and approximately fifty years later than the papacy of Pope Gelasius (492–496). In the mid-sixth century, Leontius of Byzantium traveled from Constantinople to Jerusalem, only to return to the capital afterwards. This was the time when the Empire was significantly enlarged under the reign and legislation of Justinian I. At that period, Byzantium stretched so far as to encompass southern Italy, Dalmatia, the south coast of the Black Sea, and even Tzani, lying on its furthest northeastern point. Through his legislation, Justinian strove to emphasize his anti-heretical leanings and, thus, reinforce the canons of the church and synodal acts. Leontius’ account on the Philomarianites, who offered bread in the name of Mary, points to the coeval heterodox currents—bearers of the Marian worship—even a century after the Council of Ephesus. Could Leontius have witnessed this practice somewhere near Constantinople or

⁶ Jacobs 2016, 146, and esp. note 59.

⁷ Cf. Barnes 2001, 152–164.

⁸ Another, albeit spurious, account is that of the Patriarch Eutychius of Alexandria from the 10th century. Cf. Benko 2004, 193, and Dölger 1929, 116.

⁹ Leont. of Byz. (ed. Daley, 350–351).

¹⁰ Leont. of Byz. (ed. Daley, 421).

Jerusalem? Had he just heard about it from other informants? Whatever the case, Leontius' testimony is highly relevant for our study because, two centuries after the *Panarion*, it reveals that the Collyridian type of ritual had survived in the eastern parts of the empire.

Centuries after Leontius, the long forgotten cult of the Collyridians was abruptly called into life by the renewed interest of the Byzantine scholars and 17th- and 18th-century theologians. While some of them attempted to see this sect in a positive light, others refuted them vehemently. One of the first mentions of this sect in the Byzantine period comes from Niketas Choniates (1155–1217), a state official, theologian and historian. Niketas claims in his *Thesaurus orthodoxae fidei* that the Collyridians excessively venerated the Virgin in the manner due only to God's name and cult.¹¹ Based on Niketas' account, it would seem as if the centuries-long lack of testimonies significantly thinned the theological dossier of the Collyridians. On the other hand, the full-fledged reawakening of interest in this sect and its ritual practice did not emerge before the 17th century. In this regard, one should refer to the less known, or far forgotten documents of the following theologians: Francesco Longo (*Breviarium chronologicum, pontificum, concilio-rum*, 1623), Christophorus Angelos (*Enchidrium de statu hodiernorum Graecorum*, 1630), Andreas Rivetus (*Apologia pro sanctissima virgine Maria matre Domini adversus veteres et novos Antidicomarianitas, Collyridianas, et Christianocategoros*, 1639), Adam Widenfeldt (*Avis salutaires de la Bienheureuse Vièrge Marie à ses devots indiscrets*, 1674), Andrea Magendeo (*Antibarionius Magenelis seu Animadversiones in Annales cardinalis Baronii*, 1675), Johann Caspar Schweizer (*Thesaurus ecclesiasticus e partibus graecis exhibendis quaecunque phrases*, 1728), Johann Rudolph Kiesling (*Exercitationes theologico-historicae*, 1743), and Johann Gottlob Werner (*De Collyridianorum secta*, 1745).¹²

By far the longest and most detailed assessment of the Collyridians in the Baroque period pertains to Werner's dissertation *De Collyridianorum secta*, published in 1745.¹³ This is not a peculiarity, because the topic of Mariology was unquestionably one of the most significant theological issues of the day. The disagreements between the most prominent mid-18th-century theologians were apparently *en vogue*. In the 17th century, the theological disputes between the Roman Catholics and the Protestants, revolving around the issues pertinent to Mary's

¹¹ Choniates 1580, 235.

¹² Cf. Longo 1623; Angelos 1630; Rivetus 1639; Widenfeldt 1674; Magendeo 1675; Schweizer 1728; Kiesling 1743; Werner 1745.

¹³ Werner 1745.

conception, gained in their full intensity. Popes Paul V and Gregory XV ruled, in the first quarter of the century, to be inadmissible to state that the Virgin was conceived not immaculately. Pope Alexander VII declared in 1661 that Mary's soul was free from original sin.

The proliferation of popular Virgin-inspired religiosity sees the day in Western Europe. This included various Marian pilgrimages, Salve devotions, litanies, theatre plays, hymns and processions. Marian fraternities and sororities were able to attract millions of members.¹⁴ Undoubtedly, this had an impact on the western European Protestants, so that their theologians expressly reacted to this tendency. Werner ventured to compose an entire dissertation on that topic—stimulating, thus, a new wave of interest in this cult. In this case, the Collyridian community was shortly “rehabilitated,” due to an increased interest in the development of Mariology as a distinct discipline, with all the dogmatic challenges that it could have provoked. In this new light, the cult of the Collyridians perhaps became an important link in the chain leading to the birth and flourishing of Mariology. A very important reason for that could be sought in the thriving of the popular religiosity focused on Mary, a unique sort of *religio populi*—people's popular religiosity. Historically speaking, Epiphanius' account on the Collyridians represented the earliest recorded mention of a cult and a religious practice in Christian history commemorating the Virgin Mary. This is exactly why this cult was of the utmost importance to the Roman Catholics, Protestants, and all other participants in this debate.

I. WORSHIP OR VENERATION?

Terminology has an important place in the elucidation of the Collyridian community and the distinctions between various forms of worship have been particularly prominent in this context.

Epiphanius normally uses *proskuneo* (προσκυνέω) concerning the veneration reserved for God. He also employs this verb in his admonition not to worship angels, the Virgin Mary, Elijah, or John the Baptist (Pan. II, 79, 7, 5). *Proskuneo* is employed in the biblical story of the veneration of Pharaoh's daughter, as well as in cases of idol worship. Nevertheless, Epiphanius uses this term in order to depict the religious service rendered to Mary by the Collyridians (Pan. II, 79, 9, 3). In classical Greek language, προσκύνησις has a meaning referring to “worship gods or their images,” or “prostrate before kings.” In Byzantine Greek, this term denotes “adoration” (for instance, “the adoration of the Magi”). *Proskunema* (προσκύνημα) may refer to

¹⁴ Algermissen *et al.* 1967, 577–579.

the “pilgrimage to a holy place,” while the verb *proskuneo* means “to worship.” Finally, *proskuneterion* (προσκυνητέριον) is “a place set apart for public worship.”

Interestingly, Leontius uses the verb *aposemnuno* (ἀποσεμνύω) to describe the heretical cult of the Virgin. This verb (including *semnuno* [σεμνύω], *semnoo* [σεμνώω], and the adjective σεμνός—“holy”) means “to glorify,” “to venerate,” “to celebrate,” “to honor.” However, these terms do not appear in the Byzantine Greek lexicon.¹⁵ The adjective *semnos* is an epithet for gods in antiquity denoting “saint,” “holy.” In the Bible, the terms *hagios* (ἅγιος) and *hieros* (ιερός) are used for “holy,” “saint.” In Epiphanius’ *Panarion*, *semnos* is employed to depict Mary, the most holy of all the women, as well as for marriage (*gamos*, γάμος), and only sporadically for Jesus.

On the other hand, Epiphanius’ usage of *latreia* in the *Panarion* closely relates to idolatry (εἰδολολατρεία), and is reserved for the worship of God. Epiphanius makes use of the term *latreia* in the similar sense as *proskynesis*. In late antiquity, *latreia* mainly denoted service to gods. In Byzantine Greek, it signifies “religious service or worship.”¹⁶ Epiphanius does not apply the term *douleia* to describe service to God. In the classical period, this noun was already endowed with a connotation of slavery and serfdom.

Stephen J. Shoemaker tackles previous distinctions very meticulously.¹⁷ *Proskynesis* is a term used to designate both the pre-Christian and Christian forms of veneration (*adoratio*), and it was employed in Byzantium for icon veneration as well. However, *latreia* is specifically selected to imply divine service, worship of the triune God or liturgical worship in the form of the Eucharist. This concept has been gradually developed in Christian theology from Augustine to Thomas Aquinas, and the distinction in the usage of those terms has become more pronounced only after the Seventh Ecumenical Council, and slightly earlier in respect to the worship of saints. It is thus of the utmost importance to analyze the specific terms that Epiphanius himself used, in order to elucidate the remaining lacunae pertaining to the original form of Collyridian worship.

At times, it would look as if Epiphanius himself was not quite convinced as to which particular form of worship the Collyridians had devoted to “their” Mary: ἦτοι γὰρ ὡς αὐτὴν προσκυνοῦντες τὴν Μαρίαν αὐτῇ προσφέρουσι τὴν κολλυρίδα αἱ ἀργαὶ αὐταὶ γυναῖκες ἦτοι ὑπὲρ αὐτῆς προσφέρειν ἐπιχειροῦσι τὴν προειρημένην ταύτην

¹⁵ Sophocles *et al.* 1983.

¹⁶ Cf. *Ibidem*.

¹⁷ Shoemaker 2016, 10, 242.

σαθρὰν κάρπωσιν (Pan. II, 79, 9, 3).¹⁸ Then he answers ἡ Μαρία ἐν τιμῇ, ὁ κύριος προσκυνεῖσθω (Pan. II, 79, 9, 4).¹⁹ Thus, Eriphanius makes here a terminological as well as a theological distinction, but it remains rather unclear what kind of practice the Collyridians actually performed in the course of their ritual. Was it a *time* (honor, τιμή), or a *proskynesis* (worship, προσκύνησις)?²⁰ Later on in this paper, we will relate the Collyridian *proskynesis* (offering special honor—*hyperdouleia*) to *proskynetai* as an act of veneration performed in the context of pilgrimage.

II. COLLYRIDIAN TRAJECTORIES

Strabo (64 BCE–25 CE) dedicated the eleventh book of his *Geography* to the Eurasian subcontinent, including the routes in the European and Asian hinterland.²¹ In the Roman Empire, an important road-network was maintained and extended in Thrace, linking Europe to Asian soil.²² This included the *Via Militaris*, connecting central Europe with Constantinople and the Near East. It was described in the late third-century *Itinerarium Antonini*, in the *Itinerarium Burdigalense* from 333, and in the fourth-century *Tabula Peutingeriana*. This road system included also the *Via Egnatia* and other important roads.²³ The secondary routes were predicted by taking into consideration the links established between settlements of high ecclesiastical, military or economic importance, which undoubtedly made part of an organized network system on a national level.²⁴ The Roman roads in the eastern part of the empire stretched from Anatolia further south, leading to the Holy Land; from

¹⁸ Williams 2013, 645: “Whether these worthless women offer Mary the loaf as though in worship of her, or whether they mean to offer this rotten fruit on her behalf...”

¹⁹ *Ibidem*: “Mary is to be held in honor, but the Lord is to be worshiped!”

²⁰ In the New Testament, the term *proskynesis* is widely used in the religious aspect and worship. See Danker 2009: προσκυνέω [πρός, κυνέω “to kiss” (freq. part of social ritual)] “recognize another’s prestige by offering special honor,” ordinarily through a gesture of prostration, do obeisance (to), pay homage (to)—α. to humans Matt 18.26; Acts 10.25; Rev 3.9. Especially in honor of Jesus Matt 2.2, 8, 11, 9.18, 14.33, 15.25; John 9.38. —β. to beings considered transcendent (whether identified as such expressly or by implication), ordinarily w. focus on religious aspect, worship—α. deity in monotheistic cult Matt 4.10; Luke 4.8; John 4.20f, 22b; Heb 1.6, 11.21; Rev 4.10, 5.14. —β. deity in polytheistic cult Acts 7.43. —γ. malevolent beings Matt 4.9; Luke 4.7; Rev 9.20 and freq. in Rev. —δ. angelic beings, w. gesture of prostration tantamount to religious devotion 22.8. —ε. Jesus as risen Lord Matt 28.9, 17; Luke 24.52. Hence προσκυνητής, οὔ, ὁ [προσκυνέω]—worshiper John 4.23.

²¹ Strab. *Geogr.* 5, 11 (ed. Loeb, 181–217); cf. Herod. *Hist.* 4 (ed. Brodersen).

²² For general information, see Bouzek and Graninger 2015; Lozanov 2015; Braund 2015; Rabadjiev 2015; Külzer 2011; 2019; Adams and Laurence 2005.

²³ Külzer 2011, 180–181; Salway 2005.

²⁴ Külzer 2011, 181.

the Bosphorus to Jerusalem, via Ancyra, Tarsus, Antioch, Tyre and Caesarea; through Danubian provinces, Anatolia and Syria to Egypt; from the Balkans, via the Thracian Chersonesos and the Aegean coastline, to Ephesus.²⁵ The *Itinerarium Antonini* included the maritime itinerary as well, with the lists of sea routes, channel crossings (*traiecti*), harbors and anchorages.

Epiphanius mentions Scythia together with Thrace, and is very biased in his qualifying of this region. In the *Panarion*, the term *Scythian* regularly accompanies *Barbarian* (superstition)—hence “Scythianism and Barbarianism.” Linda Ellis very persuasively explains this sort of negative association in the Roman imperial period:

The Roman Empire always felt under threat by migrating, transhumant, and displaced populations who encroached on Roman territory. The epithets, “barbarian” and “barbaricum,” are symbolic of both a “cultural limes” and the difficulty Romans had with disaffected peoples whose behavioral patterns were at variance with Roman notions of how a population should “belong” or be fixed in space. In fact, many groups foreign to the empire could, and probably were, considered peoples without a place [...]. The *barbarae nationes*, consequently, were gathered together as a psychologically manageable collectivity. The “barbarians” were not identified precisely on the basis of language, religion, geographic origin, and so on, but more likely judged as to whether their pattern of behavior was (in)compatible with the Roman perception of how a people should relate or “belong” to place. The limes, then, in Roman metageography, was also a way to define and maintain “human unrelatedness”—a frontier between place and placelessness, between the *Ordnung* of Rome and the disorder of barbaricum.²⁶

No wonder, then, that Epiphanius relates Scythians to the construction of the Babylonian Tower, a symbol of disunity and disorder among the nations: “Consulting together there they took counsel with each other to build a tower and a city. Because they had migrated to Asia from the region next to Europe they were all called Scythians in the parlance of the time” (Pan. I, 2, 10). And a little further: “They laid the foundations of the tower and built Babylon” (Pan. I, 2, 1).²⁷

Pliny the Elder, on the other hand, saw Thrace and Scythia, in the first century CE, as the northernmost regions (just below the Ocean) where the Pygmies lived, lying on the very edge of the world. The towns in Scythia Minor (Μικρά Σκυθία, modern Dobrudja in southeastern Romania) that he mentioned in his magnum opus included places with very “suggestive” names associated with female goddesses and virginity, such as Aphrodisias or Parthenopolis (*Naturalis Historia* IV, 11, 45): “The whole of this region was occupied by the Scythian tribe

²⁵ Salway 2005, 35, 40; Külzer 2019, 152.

²⁶ Ellis 2011, 246–247.

²⁷ Williams 2009, 17.

called the Ploughmen (*Scythae arotetes*), their towns being Aphrodisias, Libistus, Zygere, Rhocobae, Eumenia, Parthenopolis and Gerania, stated to have been the abode of the race of Pygmies.”²⁸ In this context, Thrace and Scythia might metaphorically represent the “ends of the earth” (especially if his “Upper Scythia”²⁹ meant Scythia Inferior, an area between the Danube and the Don and beyond the boundaries of the Roman *limes*), whereas the southern ends of the world were represented by Ethiopia and India. However, it is highly unlikely that Epiphanius himself had Pygmies in mind in the fourth century, when Christianity was already established in those areas through the endeavors of Athanasius of Alexandria. Furthermore, Epiphanius is aware of the activity of Christian groups such as the Audians in fourth-century Gothia.³⁰ We will tackle this issue more thoroughly in the context of the persecution of Christians in this region during the reign of Valens.

The meta-geographical context in which Epiphanius mentions Thrace and Scythia as the Collyridian homeland is very significant.³¹ On some occasions, these geographical terms denoted regions where the barbarians lived (in tune with popular perception), and at times, in the Christian context, these terms may have referred to the Roman provinces of Thrace and Scythia Minor, of which Epiphanius could have heard directly from Athanasius, Patriarch of Alexandria. More precisely, monasteries and monks were present in that area already in the mid-fourth century and Athanasius himself was the founder of this monastic community. He visited the territory of modern-day Bulgaria in

²⁸ Plin. *Nat. Hist.* 2 (ed. Loeb, 150–151).

²⁹ At any rate, Epiphanius’ description *καὶ τῶν ἄνω μερῶν τῆς Σκυθίας* deserves more meticulous scrutiny. This syntagm could be read as “upper parts of Scythia” or “upper regions of Scythia” and, thus, pointing to Scythia Inferior instead of Scythia Minor, hinting toward the shores of Lacus Maeotis. On the other hand, a broader syntagm *ἀπὸ τῆς Θρᾷκης καὶ τῶν ἄνω μερῶν τῆς Σκυθίας* could also mean “in Thrace and up on the coast of Scythia,” pointing instead to Scythia Minor, as a location *right above the coast* of Thrace. In this context, we also have to take into account the possibility that Epiphanius’ scribes could have rendered this geographic information in an ambiguous manner.

³⁰ Apart from the Audians, Noel Lenski (1995, 77) identifies two other Christian groups active in the conversion of Goths during the fourth century: Nicenes and Homoian “Arians.” These parties continued the debate regarding the relationship between God the Father and the Son of God in the aftermath of the Council of Nicaea (325). Homoianism (from *hómoios*, ὅμοιος) contended that the Son was only *similar* to God the Father, without reference to essence or substance (οὐσία). His relationship with the Father should be interpreted in plain biblical terms and not as consubstantiality (ὁμοουσία). Homoian Arians were also known as the Acacians, after Acacius, Bishop of Caesarea, who took an active part at the Council of Seleucia (359). The Homoians exerted much influence in the western parts of the Empire during the 360s and 370s, and were instrumental in the conversion of various Gothic groups. The Nicenes (or Neo-Nicenes) were their rival, orthodox group, whose leading figures were the Cappadocian church fathers Basil of Caesarea, Gregory of Nazianzus and Gregory of Nyssa. Epiphanius quoted the entire *Synodical Letter of Seleucia* in his chapter on the Semi-Arians (Pan. II, 73, 25, 1–10).

³¹ Cf. Ustinova 1998; Jansson 2011; Ballesteros-Pastor 2016; Erciyas 2001, 140–145.

344, at the time when he attended the Council of Serdica (modern-day Sophia).³² He was on his way back along the old Roman road *Via Diagonalis* when he had to spend the night in an old Roman fortress near Golden Meadow. He extended his stay there in order to preach to the local population and ultimately established a monastery in Čirpan, on the spot of an ancient Thracian temple. This was the first Christian monastery ever built on the territory of Europe. Two bishops, Theodulus and Olympius, held their offices in Scythia in the mid-fourth century and played very important roles in consolidating Christianity there.³³

We, therefore, contend that Epiphanius must have been very well informed about Thrace and Scythia when he mentioned them in his treatise. His Thrace and Scythia most likely implied eastern Balkans and the western Black Sea coast, where Christianity was gradually taking root.³⁴ Furthermore, the fact that Epiphanius mentions these two regions together indicates that they represented a single area in his mental topography, “geography of the mind.” Christianity was established in Scythia Minor in the third and fourth centuries, and this fact is archaeologically well documented. In addition, monks from this region were active in the coeval Christological debates. A major archaeological attestation of Christian martyrs came during the 1971 excavations beneath the paleo-Christian basilica in Niculitel (ancient *Noviodunum*), when a martyrdom was discovered. Apart from Zoticos, Attalos, Kamasis and Filippus, who suffered martyrdom under Diocletian (304–305), the relics of two previous martyrs, who witnessed and died during the persecutions of Decius (249–251), were unearthed under the crypt. By the late fifth century, Tomis on the western coast of the Black Sea had become a metropolitan bishopric, with even 14 bishoprics documented in the sixth century.³⁵

We have seen that Epiphanius’ account of the Collyridian sect provides only few details about their origin and profile, but even this limited amount of data betrays authenticity. It is clear from the *Panarion* II, 78.1.1 that this information comes from an intermediary source (“referred to my humble self by some of those pious ones”) and this is also the case with some other sects treated in his book (e.g. Ossaeans). However, the details about the Collyridian “trajectory” (from Thrace and Upper Scythia to Arabia), including the context of Epiphanius’ letter to the Arabians, provide a strong link between this bishop, his social-historical and ecclesiastical setting and his information about the Collyridians. It might perhaps appear confusing that the author of

³² See, for example, Barnes 2001.

³³ See Athanasius’ accounts in Robertson 1892, 276, 256.

³⁴ Cf. Dana 2015, esp. 256–257.

³⁵ See Stoian and Suceveanu 1987. See also Ellis 2011, 248.

the *Panarion* traces the coordinates of this sect from one remote edge of the Empire (Thrace/Scythia) to another (Arabia Petraea). However, it should be noted here that both of these regions were part of the same Praetorian Prefecture of the East in the post-Constantine I period. Furthermore, Christianity became widespread in both provinces at the time of writing the *Panarion*. Even in Scythia Minor Christianity was at home in the third and fourth centuries, with several remains of early churches found at various sites and localities.³⁶ Interestingly enough, church histories document presence of martyrs in Scythia in most of the major urban centers.

Needless to say, Epiphanius knows many details about Arabia, because he was born in Judea, led a monastery there from 335–355 and, as a bishop in nearby Cyprus, he had established a great number of local contacts and associates throughout the region. In his *Panarion*, Epiphanius mentions several other sects directly related to Arabia: Sampsaeans (Elkasaites), Ossaeans, Audians, Valesians and Antidicomarianites. Furthermore, he provides details about the worship of the goddess Kore in Alexandria and Venus in Elusa. Describing the celebrations, he points out that the people of Petra praise the virgin in Arabic, calling her Haamou, or Kore. In the same passage, he informs his readers that the festival in honor of Kore was observed in Elusa, a town in the Negev desert, as well as in Alexandria (Pan. II, 51, 22, 9–11).

We may, therefore, consider Epiphanius as a rather trustworthy source of our scanty, but important information about the Collyridians. He even makes an effort to provide them a unique name derived from their peculiar ritual practice. A greater problem in this search is the paucity of information on this community, so that most of our conclusions have to be inferred from their contextual background, including the religious and social-historical landscapes of Thrace, Scythia and Arabia. For example, if these worshipers of Mary were “at home” in both Thrace and Arabia, they probably spoke koine Greek. Their name, on the other hand, derives from an important aspect of their ritual. Furthermore, they lived outside an urban milieu and centers of power; they are, most likely, of plebeian and rural origin. Their beliefs and rituals, practiced in the *limes* of the empire, derived from the less defined, and still fluid, religious doctrines spread in the period between the first and the second ecumenical councils. Nevertheless, even the decisions of the councils, with their pertinent dogmas, would not make any significant impact on the practices of such marginal Christian groups. The Collyridians were probably a newly baptized (predominantly female) Christian community. They originated from the suspicious “barbarian” borderline, and eventually arrived in Arabia, the cradle of heresies (*Ara-*

³⁶ Ellis 2011, 248; Jansson 2011.

bia haeresium ferax). This, indeed, is more than enough to place them in the Epiphonian catalogue of sects. As itinerant devotees of Mary, they perhaps combined travel and ascetic life as their own form of spiritual activity. After all, there were monasteries in Thrace, Scythia and Arabia/Palestine (including the vicinity of Jerusalem) at the time when they undertook their journey of faith.

What would a cult like this, coming from the remote areas of the Balkans and the distant Black Sea shores, seek for in the fourth-century Arabia? This is perhaps the central question related to our attempt to reconstruct the possible Collyridian trajectory within the Praetorian Prefecture of the East. In this context, an important aspect of late fourth-century Roman historiography should be taken into consideration: the events leading to the Battle of Adrianople (378 CE), a traumatic historical experience that made an impact on the later history of the Roman Empire. At the same time, this event corresponded to the year in which Epiphanius dictated his last chapters of the *Panarion*. Peter Heather very vividly describes the period before the battle as follows:

In the summer of 376, a vast throng of people—men, women and children—suddenly appeared on the north bank of the River Danube asking for safe haven in Roman territory. One source, not our best, reports that 200,000 refugees appeared beside the river; Ammianus, that there were too many to count. They came with innumerable wagons and the animals to pull them, presumably their plough-oxen, in the kind of huge procession that warfare has generated throughout history.³⁷

Beginning with 369, those refugees included Christians from Thrace and Scythia who were the victims of Gothic persecution that took place not long before the Battle of Adrianople and the subsequent death of Emperor Valens. This is how Sozomen, the fifth-century church historian from Palestine, explains the manner in which Christians from the eastern Balkans had been persecuted by the Gothic ruler who, shortly after, contributed to the historical defeat of the Roman Army in Adrianople:

At the same period, there were many of the subjects of Phritigernes who testified to Christ, and were martyred. Athanaric resented that his subjects had become Christian under the persuasion of Ulphilas; and because they had abandoned the cult of their fathers, he subjected many individuals to many punishments; some he put to death after they had been dragged before tribunals and had nobly confessed the doctrine, and others were slain without being permitted to utter a single word in their own defense. It is said that the officers appointed by Athanaric to execute his cruel mandates, caused a statue to be constructed, which they placed on a chariot, and had it conveyed to the tents of

³⁷ Heather 2010, 154.

those who were suspected of having embraced Christianity, and who were therefore commanded to worship the statue and offer sacrifice; if they refused to do so, the men and the tents were burnt together. But I have heard that an outrage of still greater atrocity was perpetrated at this period. Many refused to obey those who were compelling them by force to sacrifice. Among them were men and women; of the latter some were leading their little children, others were nourishing their new-born infants at the breast; they fled to their church, which was a tent. The pagans set fire to it, and all were destroyed.³⁸

Epiphanius himself was well informed about the fate of his fellow Christians in this region, as indicated by his chapter on the sect of Audians:

But many members were dispersed after the death of these bishops, Uranius and Silvanus of Gothia, and their body dwindled to a small one in Chalcis by Antioch, and the Euphrates region. Indeed, the majority of them were hounded out of Gothia—not only they, but also the Christians of our kind who were there, when a great persecution was launched by a pagan king. He was a dreadful person; besides, he drove all the Christians out of those <territories> from anger at the Romans, because the Roman emperors were Christian. But neither a root of wisdom nor a shoot of faith is wanting; even if they all appear to have been driven out, there must surely be <faithful> men there. It is not possible for the spring of faith to fail. Many Audian refugees from Gothia came even here <to> our country, and lived as resident aliens for four years after that time. But they also withdrew once again <to> their Audian monasteries in the Taurus mountains, and in Palestine and Arabia. For they are widely dispersed by now but are still very few in number, and have few monasteries (Pan. II, 70, 15, 3–5).

It is, indeed, striking that Epiphanius documents the displacement of Christian refugees from Gothia (which included the territories of Thrace and Scythia) to Palestine and Arabia. These movements took place ahead of the great migrations of 376–378 and could be dated in the period between 369 and 373/374,³⁹ early enough for the Cypriot bishop to be able to include this reference in his *Panarion*. Epiphanius also makes an important chronological comment: “Many Audian refugees from Gothia came even here <to> our country and lived as resident aliens for four years after that time.” If we put “that time” at 369 CE, the year of greatest persecution of Christians in “Gothia,” we come up with the aforementioned time framework from 369 to 373 or 374, the latter being the date of Epiphanius’ writing the first chapters of his famous heresiological work. This timeline also corresponds to the reports of the Roman and Christian historians (including Epiphanius’ comrade

³⁸ Hartranft 1892, VI, 37.

³⁹ On this period of the persecution of Christians see Heather 1986; 1994; 2017; Kulikowski 2007 and Lenski 1995.

Jerome)⁴⁰ who left records about the Gothic wars and persecutions. As Kulikowski has aptly put:

Gothic Christians might come to look less like fellow subjects of the Gothic kings and more like prospective sympathisers with Valens. If, as the fifth-century church historian Socrates tells us, Valens began to send missionaries into Gothia in 369, the case against Gothic Christians was that much clearer. Persecution followed, its effects well documented in the extant sources.⁴¹

We submit that this is exactly how the Collyridian sect ended up in Arabia. Namely, the Audians were a good example how some of those Christian groups, including the wandering ascetics and other pilgrims and refugees, reached Palestine, Arabia and even Cyprus⁴² in their efforts to find safe havens within the southern provinces of the Empire. It seems, however, that Epiphanius derived his information about the Audians from an intermediary source and that he was not aware that the Collyridians, much like the Audians, were the victims of Athanaric's persecution. On the other hand, Epiphanius is very explicit when he explains that not only the Audians, but other Christians as well, were expelled from the northern provinces on Athanaric's order:

Indeed, the majority of them were hounded out of Gothia—not only they [the Audians-M.V.], but also the Christians of our kind who were there, when a great persecution was launched by a pagan king. He was a dreadful person; besides, he drove all the Christians out of those <territories> from anger at the Romans, because the Roman emperors were Christian (Pan. II, 70, 15, 4).

In our view, such a historical framework provides a very plausible explanation leading to our better understanding of the motives behind the Collyridian movement from Thrace/Scythia to Arabia. Unfortunately, this idea has been conspicuously missing from scholarship ever since Epiphanius' times.

III. PILGRIMESSES OF THE MOTHER OF GOD

The second part of our proposal concerns the very character of the Collyridian ritual. When they arrived in Arabia, probably not far from Jerusalem and, presumably, sometime between 369 and 374, the Collyridian women performed a local pilgrimage as part of their honoring

⁴⁰ Jerome also left a testimony on the persecutions in his chronicle entry for 369 CE: "Aithanaric king of the Goths persecuted Christians, killed many and drove them from their own lands to the lands of the empire" (Kulikowski 2007, 120–121).

⁴¹ Kulikowski 2007, 118.

⁴² This is Williams' suggestion: "The Audians were on Cyprus for a time, and Epiphanius would have had ample opportunity for contact with them" (Williams 2009, 412 n. 1).

the Virgin Mary. Expressions of gratitude would also be in place in the aftermath of the survived persecutions. We propose in this context that they visited the most ancient sacred space pertaining to the Mother of God in Judea, known as Kathisma (“Seat”), situated halfway from Jerusalem to Bethlehem. Thus, we regard the Collyridians as forerunners of popular religiosity linked with Mariolatry, whose examples today are present all over Latin America and Southern Europe, with a characteristic Roman Catholic emblem. Their travel took place within the same Roman prefecture, notwithstanding distance from their homes. Kathisma is the birthplace of Jesus Christ on the road outside Bethlehem, as indicated by *Protevangelion of James* (18.1), an apocryphal document from the mid-second century.⁴³ This tradition is also confirmed by the second- and fourth-century documents such as the *Dialogue with Trypho* and *Joseph the Carpenter*, both placing the nativity of Christ nearby Rachel’s tomb.⁴⁴

The sixth-century evidence places a church and a monastery at the same *locus sanctus*, relating its foundation to a Christian widow and donor Ikelia. The church of the Kathisma, dated 456 and dedicated to Mary, Mother of God, was built around a rock, the place where she took rest before her childbirth. The archeological, historical and other contextual data regarding this church are available in some of the more recent scholarly works.⁴⁵ What is important to consider in this context is that the rock in question was visited and venerated on the side of the road leading from Jerusalem to Bethlehem, while the earliest reference to this site is provided by the Armenian lectionary (417–439), the liturgical codex of the Jerusalem Christian community.⁴⁶ Not only that this fifth-century document supplies us with information about the place of the ritual, it also refers to its date: the feast of the Theotokos was celebrated on 15 August. The name of this important site is due to

⁴³ Schneemelcher 2003, 421–439.

⁴⁴ The so-called Piacenza Pilgrim in his account of the “holy places visited” confirmed this location in the sixth century (ca. 560–570): “Three miles from Jerusalem, upon the road which leads to Bethlehem, the body of Rachel lies, at the boundary of the place which is called Rama. At that very place I saw water come out of the rock in the midst of the road—I should say to the amount of nine pints—from which all men drink their fill, and yet the water is never more or less; and it is sweet to drink. It is said that this water sprang up because the Blessed Mary, when fleeing into Egypt, sat down in that place and thirsted. Here lately a church has been built” (Stewart 1887, 23).

⁴⁵ Shoemaker 2001; 2003; 2006b; 2008b; 2011; 2016; Brubaker and Cunningham 2011; Avner 2011; Mimouni 2011.

⁴⁶ This reference reads as follows: “15 August. Of Mary the Theotokos, at the second mile from Bethlehem, and this canon is performed: Psalm 131, antiphon: Rise up, Lord, from Your rest, You and the ark of Your holiness! [131.8 LXX; 132.8 NRSV] Reading from the Prophet Isaiah [7.10–16a] Reading from the Letter of the Apostle Paul to the Galatians [3.29–4.7] Alleluia, Psalm 109 [110.1–7] Gospel according to Luke [2.1–7]” (<https://www.bombaxo.com/an-early-armenian-lectionary-renoux/>). See also Renoux 1969, 180–181.

the Arabic pronunciation of a water reservoir—Bir Qadismu, from the original Greek pronunciation *kathisma*.

What we find here is the earliest recorded rite honoring the Virgin Mary not only in the ancient city of Jerusalem, but also in the entire Christian oecumene. The focus of that celebration was her virginal motherhood, in the historical period leading to, and overlapping with, the Council of Ephesus. We date this event even before the foundation of the Kathisma church and relate it to the Collyridian practice of *proskynesis* described by Epiphanius. In our view, Collyridian women did not need a church building in order to be able to perform pilgrimage to a sacred location at a given time of the year. After all, Epiphanius himself claims that they performed their ritual “on a certain day of the year” (ἐν ἡμέρᾳ τινὶ [Pan. II, 79, 1, 7]). The Lectionary, on the other hand, does not mention any temple prior to the year 439. Simply put, it was not built at that time. However, the time and the sacred space, “the coexistence of *apta diei et loco*,”⁴⁷ were sufficient preconditions for this kind of pilgrimage ritual in fourth-century Jerusalem. In fact, at the time of Epiphanius’ Collyridians, Jerusalem and its vicinity (including, of course, the Kathisma location) were definitely the most appropriate places in the entire Christian world to perform this kind of *stational* religious service, manifesting “the primacy of place in the spiritual outlook of Christians living in Palestine.”⁴⁸ John Baldovin, a pioneer in this area of liturgical studies, points out persuasively: “No doubt the most significant aspect of the Jerusalem liturgical practice [...] was its stational character. Various sites in and around Jerusalem were employed for the many services held during this period. The stations themselves shaped the liturgical celebration considerably.”⁴⁹ Cyril, the bishop and patriarch of Jerusalem between 315 and 387 CE, is considered responsible for establishing this form of liturgical practice, side by side with the development of Jerusalem as an international center of pilgrimage.

At the time of Cyril, and in line with this fourth-century ritual practice, the Collyridians could have easily visited their *locus sanctus* (which is also the *locus incarcerationis*) and performed *proskynesis* out in the open, in such a unique ecographic setting. This setting included a rock with mytho-historical significance,⁵⁰ a source of water—all situated on the road between Jerusalem and Bethlehem, the transitional point between the *illud tempus* of the Hebrew Bible and the imminent *kairos* of the nascent religion. In this context, the Collyridian women were

⁴⁷ Smith 1992, 94.

⁴⁸ Wilken 1992, 113.

⁴⁹ Baldovin 2010, 39.

⁵⁰ Theodosios the Pilgrim, ca. 510–530, first mentioned this improvised seat of the Theotokos: ... *domina Maria mater domini, dum iret in Bethleem, descendit de asina et sedit super petram et benedixit eam* (Theodosios 1882, 28).

pilgrims, much like *panegyristes* who frequented temples and other holy places of Artemis of Ephesus, Bendis of Thrace, Cybele of Hierapolis, Aphrodite, Ma of *Comana Pontica* or Chersonesus, and many other goddesses all over the ancient Mediterranean world. For these women, this is a rite of passage with its ultimate transformative dimension: it affects both their individual and collective identity. They travelled from the *limes* to the holy center, as it were: the Kathisma rock is a prototypical, ecographic and mytho-historical object, the site of the “original event.” This is the place of power, grace, redemption, healing, rest and remembrance, a new beginning, an *arche*. The Collyridian women went through an ultimate, total experience on the road to Kathisma, after probably visiting some other *loca sancta* near Jerusalem. It is, indeed, impossible to conceive of another locality of greater importance for the worshippers of Mary who had crossed so many miles in order to perform their peculiar ritual. Eventually, they ended up in the Holy Land, at the most significant spot in the entire inhabited world (*oecumene*), as the Romans conceived it, where they could have expressed the full force of their Mariolatry. No other place in this region possessed such a historical, mythological and ecographic capacity to provide their ultimate experience. This is where it all started.

Let us also recall the Hypapante (Candlemass), one of the ancient feasts held in Jerusalem and celebrated in the fourth century at Golgotha.⁵¹ Widow Ikelia, most likely with the blessing of Bishop Juvenal from Jerusalem, introduced this kind of candle ceremony at the Kathisma church soon after his return from the first council of Ephesus. Emperor Justinian, who included the candle procession in the holy calendar of Constantinople, made this tradition official in Byzantium.

Now, what are the implications of this new hypothesis regarding the background and activity of Epiphanius’ Collyridians? First, it appears that the Bishop of Salamis knew what he was talking about. This was his domicile geographic area, including the monastery that he headed for two decades (only 60 kilometers away from the Kathisma). This entire Mariolatry rite of the Collyridians was new to him, a sort of odd religious practice, important for his polemic concerning the status of the Virgin Mary and the proper ways of her veneration. It was so novel to him, that it actually represented the first historical report of a ritual dedicated to the Theotokos. The fact that he did not mention the precise location of the Collyridian rite is most likely due to his use of an intermediary source. Nevertheless, even this partial information was sufficient for his main polemical purpose: to contrast the Collyridians’ excessive form of worship with the lower esteem of the Virgin Mary among the Antidicomarianites who “dared to speak insolently of this

⁵¹ Avner 2011, 22.

holy and blessed Ever-virgin” (Pan. II, 78, 23, 2). In that context, it was not so significant to know where and when the Collyridian ritual had been performed: it was an inappropriate form of *latreia* directed towards a human being. This is why Epiphanius had to conclude: “Mary is to be held in honor, but the Lord is to be worshiped!” (Pan. II, 79, 9, 4).⁵²

Second, even more importantly, this hypothesis provides a religious rationale for the connection between Thrace/Scythia and Arabia in the late fourth century, in the aftermath of Athanaric’s persecution of Christians. The locus of the future Kathisma Church did not have a proper *templum*, but it was nevertheless a veneration spot, due to its pre-history and apocryphal tradition (starting with the *Protevangelium of James*). This was the practice recorded in the transitional period between late antiquity and early Byzantium.

Third, the Collyridian pilgrims visited the place of rest of the Virgin Mary prior to her delivery of the Son of God. Her sacred “seat” became a Christian temple over time, while during the fourth century this may also have been a setting for a smaller altar used for the Collyridian bread-offering. Their *proskynesis* (offering special honor, later known as *hyperdouleia*) was linked to *proskynetai*—their pilgrim worship.⁵³ We align ourselves with the view of Joan Taylor, claiming that “archaeological and literary evidence taken together bears out the impression that in the Late Roman period sites that were especially holy to Christians were not venerated prior to the fourth century,” and that “the historical and archaeological evidence indicate the beginning of the fourth century as the time at which pilgrimage to certain Christian holy sites began, and that the sites themselves were developed.”⁵⁴ On the other hand, the Armenian lectionary is a reliable testimony for this place of worship in the early fifth century. Despite the Ikelia’s church dating ca. 456, the performance of the Collyridian ritual, accompanied by pilgrimage, could be reasonably traced back to the late fourth century.

One should also bear in mind that the rock was a very important sacred object among the Arabs even before the advent of Islam: the one celebrated in Mecca was the site of Abraham’s/Ibrahim’s biblical step, whereas the other, venerated at the Kathisma site, was Mary’s place to rest soon before the nativity event.⁵⁵ Both stones were remembered as holy sites between the Christian and Muslim Arabs. In both cases,

⁵² Williams 2013, 645.

⁵³ On the term *proskynetai* in relation to pilgrimage, see, for example, Lightfoot 2005.

⁵⁴ Cited in Brubaker and Cunningham 2011, 18.

⁵⁵ Another commemorative site of early Islam, in the proximity of the Prophet’s Mosque in Medina, was dedicated to a stone allegedly used by Muhammad as his resting spot. In the mid-eighth century, it was believed that this site was helpful to women who had troubles in getting pregnant, as is often the case even today with sacred topography related to the Virgin Mary. See Munt 2014, 112.

we contend, pilgrims frequented these stones even before the building of appropriate sanctuaries.⁵⁶ The Christian Arab federates from a little bishopric of the Parembolē (only about ten kilometers to the east from the Kathisma site) normally performed their pilgrimage to Jerusalem and its environs in the proto-Byzantine period:

The sources suggest that some villages in the vicinity, such as Bethaboudis and Lazarium,⁵⁷ were ethnically Arab or partly so; the names of some Christian Arabs, such as Tha'laba and 'Urqub, have been preserved in the sources. These certainly would have made pilgrimage to Jerusalem, being so close to it, as did the Christian Arabs of Palaestina Tertia, Rhomaioi, known to us from the churches built in the cities of the Negev. The six of them might be termed the Hexapolis of Palaestina Tertia.⁵⁸

Those Christian Arabs of Palestine (considered, by a 19th-century church historian, as nomads converted by St. Euthymius)⁵⁹ had their first bishop appointed by Juvenal, Patriarch of Jerusalem (ca. 427).⁶⁰ His name was Peter and his title was Bishop of the Parembolē (meaning the "Camps"), because the local Arabs had lived in extra-mural camps or peri-urban settlements dispersed all over the countryside.⁶¹

Let us now sum up our main argument. The Armenian Lectionary confirms that the Feast of the Theotokos on the Kathisma location is the first and most ancient Marian feast in Jerusalem exclusively linked to the Mother of God, independently of Christ (his nativity, epiphany, resurrection). At the same time, there is no other source indicating such an early celebration of Mary outside of Jerusalem. The Collyridian ritual celebrating Virgin Mary, recorded by Epiphanius in the mid-370s, is the most ancient religious cult in history dedicated solely to Mary, the Mother of God. Additionally, Epiphanius located the Collyridians in the

⁵⁶ The Arab poet Al-A'sha mentions, for example, two Ka'bas in the sixth century, as the competitive places of pilgrimage in the Byzantine period: the first was a shrine for Christians in Najrān (south of Mecca), a square domical building in the form of the *martyrion*; the other was a shrine of the Arabian polytheistic worshippers in Mecca itself (Shahid 2006, 395). It is also very interesting that some seventh-century Christians from Najrān, who had visited Muhammad, were influenced by the doctrine of the sect known as *Maryāmiyyān*. Their members apparently considered Mary a person of the Holy Trinity. See Neuwirth and Sells 2016, 301. The Qur'ān, on the other hand, "gives its support against Mariolatry, while at the same time it recognizes the importance of Mary as the vessel chosen by God for the birth of his Christ" (*Ibidem*).

⁵⁷ Lazarium (Bethany, al-Eizariya), known as the place of biblical Lazarus (Jn 11.1–46), already had a church between 333 and 390, that is, at the time of the Collyridians. Egeria the pilgrim, in her itinerary, recounts a liturgy celebrated there circa 410 CE. See Gingras 1970, 102–103. This church served as a station point, especially busy and prominent during the Easter celebration: e.g. on Saturday before Palm Sunday—the Lazarus Saturday.

⁵⁸ Shahid 1998, 374.

⁵⁹ Fleury 1844, 28.

⁶⁰ Shahid 2006, 40–47.

⁶¹ Fleury 1844, 28.

Roman province of Arabia, not far from the Kathisma site.⁶² Historically and methodologically, these facts could be linked together, and our hypothesis provides such a link. Furthermore, the *Protevangelium of James* (17.2–3), the mid-second-century document, refers to the locus of the future Kathisma church. In all likelihood, this apocryphal tradition had some significance for the local population prior to the construction of the church. This belief could have initially prompted visits to the Kathisma site, while later on (beginning with the early fourth century and state tolerance of Christianity) the initial observance could have evolved into a local pilgrimage. Indigenous Arab Christians must have been familiar with this practice: they could have performed their pilgrimage at least once a year even before the construction of Ikelia's *Ecclesia Kathismatis*. After all, the church would probably have never been built if it were not for the living presence of the same tradition. Interestingly enough, Hesychius of Jerusalem (died ca. 450?) read his Marian homilies, recommended by the Armenian Lectionary, for the Feast of the Theotokos. The editor of these homilies, Michel Aubineau, assumes that he read them at the Kathisma location even before the building of Ikelia's church.⁶³

At the time of Jerome and Epiphanius, an entire religious infrastructure emerged in Bethlehem and its surroundings in order to accept numerous visitors, travelers and pilgrims from all over the world. This included special hostels—*diversorium peregrinorum*. It would be reasonable to assume that even the Collyridians had a place to stay upon their arrival from some Arabian town, while other pilgrims came from as far away as India, Persia and Ethiopia.⁶⁴

Therefore, this is an example of a ritual accompanied by a pilgrimage, as is normally the case even today throughout the religious world. The Feast of the Theotokos was celebrated in summer (15 August), in an open air, with the presence of pilgrims from all over the Empire and beyond, using their land- and maritime-routes during the season when it was possible to sail long-distance (from April to October in the Mediterranean). The ritual itself was closely related to the idea of birth-giving, motherhood, as well as to the continual virginity of Mary: hence, the frequent mentions of the term *aieparthenos* in the pertinent passages of the *Panarion*. However, theology was most likely of secondary importance for the participants in this ritual, half a century before the ecumenical Council of Ephesus. This was an example of popular devotion, pilgrimage, fitting perfectly within the plebeian and rural background of the

⁶² We have already argued that Epiphanius perceived Arabia as a region “on the borders of Palestine” (Pan. II, 66, 1, 7).

⁶³ Aubineau 1978, 137, 145–149. See also Sivan 2008, 234.

⁶⁴ Cain 2010, 112.

Collyridians. They were Christians from Thrace and Scythia, probably the worshippers of some local goddess before the advent of Christianity. Nevertheless, they represented an unusual phenomenon, perhaps even a concern, to some ecclesiastical authorities and, thus, they found their way to Epiphanius' album of heresies.

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